

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF

ENGINEERING MATHEMATICS: THEORY AND APPLICATION

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Hungary Academic Member of ATINER

Athens E-mail: kurdics@nyf.hu

CONTACT

Professor of Computational Engineering

Mathematics and Numerical Analysis

Faculty of Engineering

Zagazig University

Zagazig

P. O. 44519

Egypt

<http://iejemta.com/>

Email: sgamil@zu.edu.eg

PROSPECTS AND SOME PROBLEMS OF DIGITIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN

Jumayev Askar Khaydarovich - Distinguished Lecturer in the Department of
“Digital Economics” Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service.

email:askardjumayev@gmail.com

Abstract: This article examines the processes of digitalization in the Republic of Uzbekistan and some problems associated with the implementation of these tasks, and also indicates ways to solve them. Thoughts and opinions are offered on how to digitalize socio-economic systems in the context of globalization processes occurring in the world, regulate, finance and control systems based on digital platforms. It also offers some recommendations for ensuring the information security of society.

Keywords: digitalization, IT industries, system analysis, information technology, blockchain, artificial intelligence, digital platform, STEM research centers, infrastructure.

Introduction

Currently, many developing and developing countries in the world are digitalizing various sectors and spheres of society to increase the intensity of economic growth. We see that the main reason for this is that the quality of production and provision of services in the social sphere, as well as public services based on digital components, is acquiring particular importance, as these components are gradually increasing the efficiency of their activities. Specifically, regarding this, Mariana Mazzucato, Director of the Institute for Innovation and Social Goals at University College London, suggests that "Europe's recovery will create a dynamic process that will lead to the following: setting bold national goals, including the digitalization of public services, and expanding the private sector through service procurement programs" [2]. In fact, European countries are currently moving forward in terms of social, economic, cultural, educational, educational, medical, and

digitalization of public administration, and we see that this process is becoming one of the main factors in the development of society.

In our Republic, the digitalization of the public administration system and the digitalization of existing information, control in education, healthcare, tax and customs services, and social infrastructure are being carried out gradually and consistently. In this regard, the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, whose strategic goal is "the implementation of more than 400 information systems, electronic services, and other software products in various spheres of regional socio-economic development" [1], demonstrates that the digitalization of socio-economic systems represents one of the most pressing tasks.

Literature analysis on the topic

Many economists have conducted research on digitalizing the socio-economic system, improving its infrastructure, and forming and developing a legislative framework. However, in our country, we see a lack of research into the process of its operation, certain shortcomings in legislation, increasing the population's knowledge and skills in using digital platforms, and ways to digitalize social and economic systems. For example, in modern scientific literature, digitalization is described as an integral part of the modern global economy, leading to more rational resource management (Antikainen, 2018), the optimization of business management models (Rachinger, 2018), and supporting structural changes (Heavin & Power, 2018).

In general, the digital economy is characterized by production flexibility, easy access to information, zero marginal costs, and potentially serious consequences. These indicators can already be observed in advanced digital industries - the IT industry, communications, and leisure in a broader sense. EU countries view digitalization as a key driver of competitiveness, economic development, and employment growth [6]. Furthermore, the pace of digitalization in the banking sector

is developing at an unprecedented pace. This implies revolutionary changes in banking information processing systems, qualification requirements, and financial services. The model of the banking system has changed, which has made it possible to reduce costs and increase the productivity of financial services. At the same time, digitalization in the banking sector involves the accumulation of intangible capital, which is not always correctly valued in capital markets and thereby creates "bubbles," as well as the lack of confidentiality, regulation, supervision, and the inability to ensure equal conditions for all participants in the banking market, which makes it impossible to assess the serious problems associated with this.

Digitalization is responsible for the individualization of modern production. In turn, this means that product development is individual for each client. Production includes visualization, production modeling, ergonomics and human factor analysis, a holistic approach to product and process design, and product design that is sensitive to process constraints and capabilities. Modern production (for example, chemical processing) is impossible without data analysis, network systems, artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, business process digitalization, and all the features of Industry 4.0 (Kockmann, 2018) [7].

Furthermore, the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" strategy adopted by the head of our state, which defines the socio-economic development of our country, includes priority goals for the digitalization of various industries and spheres, and it has been determined that by 2030, the share of the digital economy in GDP may reach 30%.

Research methodology

In the process of researching this article, research on the development and organization of banks and digital banks in the context of the digital economy was analyzed and studied. Its study was also carried out based on the use of a number of methods, including the results of a monographic analysis of foreign experience, monographic research, and analysis and synthesis based on economic methods such

as systems analysis, which have acquired significant importance in revealing the possibilities of digitalizing the economy.

Analysis and results

Digitalization processes have changed not only economic but also social views on the world. The digital age is defined by a constant flow of information, knowledge, ideas, and innovations. Developed countries that have completed industrialization are successfully digitalizing their economies. They are rapidly developing innovative technologies in which artificial intelligence, automation, and digital platforms dominate. Digitalization is traditionally regarded as a positive sign of societal development. However, digitalization has penetrated so deeply into all aspects of public life that the question arises as to whether human rights to privacy and anonymity may be violated [8].

At the current stage of development, it is possible to assess the advantages and disadvantages of digitalization, as well as to state that it is impossible to effectively manage the state and its economy without actively implementing the latest developments in the fields of informatics, electronics, communications and telecommunications, and radio broadcasting. Digitalization helps reduce poverty and the digital divide between all social groups and strata [9].

The concepts of "digital technology" and "digital economy" have entered the scientific vocabulary of the 21st century thanks to technological changes related to the "fusion" of telecommunications, information and communication technologies, and innovations. Currently, digital technologies are changing relations between economic entities in the fields of energy, construction, banking, transport, retail trade, education, healthcare, media, and security. The complexity of social development institutions and relations, often based on modern digital technologies, leads to an exponential increase in information flows and actualizes the problem of forming a digital economy. It is precisely the ongoing processes that allow for the creation of a

new type of economy that accelerates the introduction of innovations into the economy and social life through the production, processing, storage, transmission, and use of information, as well as information growth.

Currently, the development of electronic commerce is linked to the globalization of the economy. The rapid growth in global trade volume, capital mobility, and its concentration occurred in the 1990s, when the use of information and communication technologies expanded and electronic commerce became a typical business activity for large corporations. The data in Figure 1 show an average growth rate of 6 percent.

Indicators of the digitalization of socio-economic systems, the "digital leap," and the transition to a higher technological level of development for macro-systems (e.g., states) may also include:

- ability to develop and implement digital technologies, as well as information and communication technologies, and the presence of professional personnel [17];
- use of appropriate equipment and technologies, and dissemination of technologies between citizens and enterprises;
- gradual recovery of domestic demand for technologies, market "successes" in various spheres of life and the economy, the presence of local representative offices, manufacturers of machinery, and distributors of high-tech equipment;
- sufficient level of system integration of technological products and services: covers processes from design to the comprehensive implementation of various technologies, software, and technical means.

Figure 1. Global dynamics of e-commerce volume [9].

This is a key element of the digital economy and a decisive factor in the growth of the entire economy, especially the digital industry as a technology producer. In many industries, digital technologies form the basis of marketing and production strategies. Their transformative power is changing traditional business models, production chains, and processes, leading to the emergence of new products and services, platforms, and innovations [9]. It is important to create conditions and appropriate information, marketing, and tax incentives for enterprises, small and medium-sized businesses, and industry so that they can change significantly. Digital infrastructures related to digital technologies must be accessible both from an organizational-technological perspective and from a financial-economic perspective, i.e., by creating tools that stimulate business digitalization. The result of such activities will be the modernization of the economy, its restoration, and the enhancement of its competitiveness.

Priority work is also being carried out in our country to digitalize the education sector. The importance of digital components for the large-scale development of preschool, school, higher, postgraduate, or distance education systems in the modern era is considered significant. It should be noted that we have the potential for large-scale changes in other areas of education as well. To this end, the work to be carried

out in our country to implement the digitalization of the education sector consists of the following:

- creation of educational resources and digital platforms that support interactive and multimedia content for wide use by educational institutions and students, including the use of automation tools for the main processes of educational institutions;

- development and implementation of innovative computer learning tools and equipment for creating a digital learning environment (STEM research centers, laboratories, inclusive classrooms, blended learning classes) [11];

- ensuring broadband Internet access for students and students in all educational institutions;

- development of a full distance learning format using cognitive and multimedia technologies.

It should be noted that the digitalization of socio-economic spheres is necessary to monitor public health through the digitalization of the healthcare sector, to take timely countermeasures, and to ensure the health of future generations.

Digitalization of medicine is important for the development of the industry and the effective provision of medical services. Digital medicine ensures interaction between patients, medical workers, and institutions using information, communication, and digital technologies. Translating medical documentation into an electronic format is one of the priorities of digital medicine. The development of a fully digital medical platform is an important step toward the digitalization of medical and related services, as well as the mutual cooperation of operators in this field.

A digital medical platform is a dynamic collection of systematically organized electronic information about an individual patient's health status, ensuring information exchange between departments, as well as the confidentiality and

security of data storage [20]. The implementation of telesystems for providing remote medical services to citizens and supporting doctors in rural areas remains a crucial element in the development of digital medicine. Medicine is changing: periodic diagnostics are being conducted online, the Internet of Things allows for the use of sensors for continuous monitoring of human health, and medical and related service operators are becoming participants in digital platforms. All of this affects the quality, efficiency, and functionality of the medical care system.

Conclusions and proposals. Digitalization requires new forms of partnership and cooperation in various fields at all levels of the economy and society, and this digitalization must ensure equal access to information and knowledge services provided based on information, communication, and digital technologies for every citizen. The creation of digital infrastructures for socio-economic systems is a key factor in expanding citizens' opportunities to utilize the global information environment and knowledge. In this regard, based on the results of the study conducted above, we consider it appropriate to implement the following proposals and recommendations:

- Digitalization should be aimed at creating advantages in various spheres of life, including improving the quality of healthcare and education services, creating new jobs, developing entrepreneurship, agriculture, and transport, environmental protection, and natural resource management;

- digitalization must be carried out through economic growth through increasing the efficiency, productivity, and competitiveness of digital technologies, which implies the digital transformation of economic sectors and spheres of activity, as well as acquiring new competitive qualities and characteristics;

- Digitalization should serve the development of the information society and mass media. Creating content adapted to national or regional needs contributes to

social, cultural, and economic development, as well as strengthening the principles of an information society and democracy;

- Digitalization must focus on international, European, and regional cooperation. The conscious and full implementation of information, communication, and digital technologies will lead to their integration into global systems and infrastructures;

- Digitalization must be carried out alongside the improvement of public safety. Information security, cybersecurity, protection of personal data, confidentiality, and user rights, strengthening and protecting trust in cyberspace, as well as digital development and the prevention, elimination, and high-quality management of associated risks are mandatory conditions;

- the main focus of the government in the field of digitalization should be on the formation of a comprehensive management system, and its main tasks should be to correct the shortcomings of market mechanisms, eliminate institutional and legislative barriers, attract appropriate investments, stimulate the development of digital infrastructure and meet the needs of enterprises and the population in the use of digital technologies.

However, it should be noted that the lack of simultaneous digitalization, local software, equipment, and development projects that are not monitored at the regulatory level can affect national security. Within the framework of the information war problem, the most dangerous transboundary and political threats to the information security of the state have long been studied. Therefore, digitalization projects should be considered in the context of ensuring information security at various levels of society.

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